

CONFLICTS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF RELIGIOUS SPONSORED PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS. EXPERIENCE FROM KENYA

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Abstract:

Religious sponsors have in the past contributed immensely to the growth of education in Kenya. The purpose of this study was to find out the factors that lead to the management conflicts between religious sponsors and other stakeholders in public secondary schools in Nandi South Sub-County. The purpose of this study was to find out the factors that lead to the emerging conflicts between religious sponsors and head teachers, education officials, parents and schools' Boards of Governors in the management of public secondary schools in Nandi South Sub-County. The survey research design was adopted for this study. The study population comprised of all the 38 religious sponsored Public Secondary Schools in Nandi South Sub-County, 38 Board of Governors' Chairmen, 38 Parents and Teachers' Association Chairmen, 38 head teachers and 342 teachers from the same schools, 6 education secretaries of the schools' religious sponsors and 5 Assistant Education Officers. The saturated sampling technique was used by this study. Questionnaires and in-depth interviews were used to collect data. These instruments were first tested for reliability through a pilot study and the use of the coefficient of internal consistency of the split-half reliability method. Validity was established through the application of face validity procedures. Quantitative data were analyzed critically in themes as guided by study objectives to establish relationships among responses. The findings of the study indicated that most of the conflicts involved religious sponsors on one hand and other stakeholders. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education sensitizes the public secondary schools' church sponsors, head teachers, Board of Governors and its field officers with

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regards to the correct interpretation of the Education Act as a tool in secondary schools' management. The findings of this study would therefore provide a useful reference for educational administrators and managers.

Keywords: secondary schools' management, conflict, religious sponsors

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The success of every school depends on its management. This is also essential for the development of any education system and for education to achieve its stated goals for the benefits of a nation. Schools, whether public or private have a number of stakeholders in their activities. According to the Commonwealth Secretariat (2000), the governance of a school is done through a coalition of interests performing different functions all aimed at enabling the school to operate and achieve its aims. This is in line with the observation by Owens (1987) that people in organizations have definite roles to perform and many interactive factors help to determine precisely their particular performances.

According to Government of Kenya (Republic of Kenya, 1968), the Education Act spells out the roles of sponsors in the management of Public Secondary Schools. However, reports indicate that all is not well as regards relations between religious sponsors and other stakeholders like head teachers, parents and education officers in the management of public secondary schools.

The Report of the Committee reviewing the education system in Kenya chaired by Davy Koech (Republic of Kenya, 1999) reveals that there are a number of conflicts involving religious sponsors, parents and Parents and Teachers' Association officials, head teachers and Boards of Governors.

Several instances of conflicts in church sponsored schools have been reported. Matoke and Barasa (2001) for example reported an impasse that had arisen between the Catholic Church and the Ministry of Education over the closure of five Parochial Schools which had gone to a second week. The impasse was rooted on the grounds that Catholic Church Officials had complained about government violation of the provision of the Education Act which requires that they should be involved in most of the decision making processes on matters affecting the management of schools.

Whereas it is the Ministry of Education to appoint principals in consultation with the sponsors, it is now the other way round. Matoke and Barasa (2001) also reported a case where the African Inland Church (AIC) had been accused of frustrating

government efforts to resolve a crisis at Kapsabet Girls High School in Nandi North District. The church had refused to recognize the appointment of the Board of Governors (BOG) yet it was involved in the BOG's nomination process.

The Nandi South District Secondary Schools' Heads Association (NSDSSHA, 2005) manual quoted the District Education Officer, during the Heads' annual meeting, reiterating to the head teachers of the secondary schools in Nandi South District the need to have good working relations between them and the sponsors. The District Education Officer (DEO.) cited the case of Meteitei Secondary school where the AIC Education Secretary had asked the District Education Office to nullify the BOG nomination exercise yet the secretary was involved in the same.

When reports of the conflicts in management of schools come up, they need to be urgently investigated with the aim of bringing about harmony and understanding amongst those involved. By so doing, the continuity and growth of education in this country would be ensured.

However, there have been emerging conflicts in the management of Public Secondary Schools that were founded by religious sponsors. Yet, the specific conflicts and the effects they may have on management of the schools particularly in Nandi South District, have not been systematically investigated or documented and solutions sought. This study was committed to that end.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

It cannot be disputed that religious sponsors have contributed a great deal to the growth of education in this country. Indeed, in recognition of this fact, the government provided for their inclusion in the management of Public Secondary Schools in the Education Act of 1968. As time passed by, however, there were increasing reports of conflicts between them and other stakeholders like parents, education officials and head teachers despite their roles being spelt out clearly in the Education Act.

The background information reveals several cases of emerging conflicts involving religious sponsors and other education stakeholders. For example in 1998 and 2005, the AIC sponsor wanted the head teacher of Sochoi secondary school to disallow Seventh Day Adventist (SDA) students from conducting their services while in 2005, the AIC education Secretary wanted to force the BOG nomination panel of Meteitei school to appoint certain individuals to the Board against the normal procedure. In Aldai Girls High School, the Anglican Church of Kenya sponsor wanted the Headmistress to be transferred because she had refused to pay salary to a chaplain sent to the school.

Cases like this impact negatively on the academic growth of the concerned schools in particular and Nandi south as a Sub-County in general. Despite the existence

of the aforementioned conflicts, no systematic study known to the researcher has ever been done to find out and document the specific conflicts in religiously sponsored public secondary schools' management.

2. Existing Literature and Research

2.1 Introduction

In this section, a review of literature on religious sponsors and conflicts in Secondary schools' management is presented in two parts namely;

- Historical background of Religious Schools' management conflicts;
- Specific conflicts in schools management.

2.2 Historical Background of Religious Schools' Management Conflicts

Religion, especially Christianity, has always been concerned with the education of man (Scanlon, 1966). Missionaries take the credit of setting up the first educational institution in Kenya (Ayodo, 1977). The Church Missionary Society (CMS) was the first to set up a school in Kenya as early as 1844 but their activities were confined to the coastal region (Shidende, 1996). The major contribution of the Missionaries was their great effort directed at attracting the African children to school (Ogola, 1996). In a study on Kenya's post-independence educational objectives, Ogola (1996) also mentioned that, at times, parents were paid so as to allow their children to go to school. This was because African parents by then had not realized the benefits of formal education that we aspire for today.

At first, the colonial administrators were content to leave educational matters to the Church Missions (Eshiwani, 1993). But the 1920s saw increased government interest, with the government stepping in; partly to respond to the outcries of the Africans for an academic type of education beyond the religious education the missions were offering (Shidende, 1996).

The increased government interest in education was in the form of instituting a department for education in 1911 through which the government started giving grants to the missions. These were increased from 1919 when a pattern of cooperation was instituted between the government and the mission in which the former supplied more grants while the missionaries catered for the teachers and management (Ayodo, 1977).

In time, there evolved two categories of schools, that is, those run entirely by the voluntary organizations referred to as unaided and those run with the help of the colonial government referred to as aided (Abreu, 1982). The government aided schools developed racial characteristics in the form of separate schools for Europeans, Asians

and Africans. Most of the Africans got their education needs from mission schools as the few government schools for the Africans could not cater for the increased demand for education (Abreu, 1982).

The situation of a disintegrated education system was largely what was inherited at the onset of independence. This was because education for Africans was regarded as serving a social rather than an economic function (Stabler, 1969). At independence however, this changed with the government setting up a Commission of Inquiry popularly known as the Ominde Commission (Republic of Kenya, 1964). It was to look into the issue of racial and religious segregation in schools, localizing of the curriculum and medium of instruction (Sifuna, 1990). The government and missionary cooperation in education did not however radically change at the attainment of independence. Sifuna (1976) notes that for a period of five years or so after independence missionaries continued to have considerable control over the school system.

It was the Education Act of 1968 that clearly spelt out how schools were to be managed in the newly independent Kenya (Chepkwony, 1987). In a study on the roles of the National Council of Churches of Kenya (NCCCK) in development, the researcher's findings indicate that, the Education Act of 1968 was meant to give the government the control over management and policy of education. This was to enable it realize its manpower development and provision of social services to all. Wainaina (1991) highlights this in a study on Christian religious education in Kenyan Secondary Schools. The researcher's findings indicate that, the Education Act specifically gave churches the powers to sponsor their former schools. These include the functions of being consulted on staffing issues and representation in schools' Boards of Governors.

2.3 Specific Conflicts in Schools' Management

Conflict is a pervasive aspect in both professional and social interactions. As long as there is a human element present, conflict is certain (Waitchella, Supiah and Radman, 2006). Conflicts occur when compelling groups, objectives, needs or values clash and aggression although not necessarily violence is a result (Randall, 1994). Mutsotso (2004) in his study on the role of social education and ethics in the management of students' violence in secondary schools found out that some people in schools' management were involved in students' indiscipline.

He found out that, members of schools' Boards of Governors with vested interest in some schools incited students to go on strike in those schools. They did that so as to achieve their own goals. Political interference and feuds among community members also contributed to school unrests.

Osure (1996, cited by Koskei, 2004) in a study on the PTA and BOG sought to establish their functional relationships and the implications for effective secondary school management in Kisumu District. His research revealed that there was no clear cut definition of the management structure in secondary schools. He also found out that, the roles and boundaries of BOGs and PTAs in the management of development funds in public secondary schools were neither specified nor clearly demarcated. As a result of that, conflicts and uncertainties had arisen with other participants in schools' management.

In its 2003 research report on religious freedom in public schools, the standing committee on Human Rights (cited in International Religious Freedom, 2005) noted that the African Inland Church (AIC) infringed on students' freedom of worship. It also noted that the AIC sponsors a number of schools most of which are public. The study found out that the AIC sponsors compelled all students admitted to its schools to adhere to its beliefs, which contradicted the constitution.

Okotoni and Okotoni (2003) carried out a study on conflict management in secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The study identified several types of conflicts. They included, conflict between management and staff; between staff and students, between communities and schools and inter-personal conflicts. The present study however concentrated on conflicts that occurred in public secondary schools that were religiously sponsored.

According to Eregha (2006, in Okotoni and Okotoni, 2003) however, conflicts in schools' management occur due to different leadership styles employed by school principals and variations in schools' structures. Where a school principal puts in place a climate of trust and respect amongst all stakeholders, then conflict is minimized. That also goes hand in hand with conflict management measures that are put in place by the principal. That is because institutions where conflicts are well managed, a conducive work place is created for all stakeholders that in turn results in stimulated team spirit and increased productivity.

Canavan and Monahan (2001) also identified various school management conflicts. These included those that arose over the imposition of decisions by authorities without due consultation with staff and students. Other conflicts included those that arose as a result of a great communication gap between administration and students. The present study looked at conflicts that arose in the management of public secondary schools that were religiously sponsored.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to find out the factors behind the emergence of conflicts in the management of public secondary schools in Nandi south District that had religious sponsors. The study investigated how interactions between sponsors, head teachers, teachers, Boards of Governors and Parents and Teachers Association and education officers in religiously sponsored public secondary schools were leading to conflicts in management.

3.1 Research question

Only one research question was applied here since the others were beyond the scope of this particular study. The research question was: *“What specific conflicts can be observed from some religious sponsors, education officers, Boards of Governors, Parents and Teachers’ Association and head teachers in the management of Public Secondary Schools?”*

4. Population

The study population comprised of 38 head teachers, 342 teachers, 38 BOG and 38 PTA chairmen from the schools shown in Table 1, 5 Assistant Education Officers (AEOs), from the 5 administrative divisions and 6 religious sponsors’ Education Secretaries of the various denominations in the district giving rise to a total of 467 respondents.

Table 1: Types of Schools in Nandi South

Sponsor	Number Of Schools				
	Boys	Girls	Co-educ.	Total	%
Roman Catholic	1	3	10	14	36.8
P.A.G	--	--	2	2	5.3
A.I.C.	2	4	4	10	26.3
S.D.A	--	--	1	1	2.6
A.C.K	1	3	5	9	23.7
Orthodox	--	--	2	2	5.3
Grand Total	4	10	24	38	100%

5. Setting and Methodology

The study was carried out in Nandi South Sub-County, which is one of the districts in the Rift Valley Province, Kenya at an altitude of 1660M above sea level. It is bordered by Uasin Gishu County to the East, Nandi North to the West and Nyando to the South.

Kisumu District borders it to the South West, Kericho District on its Northern side while Vihiga County borders it on its Western side. It has five administrative divisions that also serve as education divisions namely; Aldai, Nandi Hills, Tindiret, Kaptumo and Lessos. The public secondary schools in this region are mainly sponsored by Christian Church denominations like the African Inland Church (AIC), The Anglican Church of Kenya (ACK), The Seventh Day Adventist Church (SDA), Orthodox Church and the Roman Catholic Church. Currently, only Christian denominations sponsor secondary schools in the district.

6. Methodology

This was a descriptive study that adopted the survey research design. The descriptive approach of survey design of research is concerned with collecting data about the occurrence or instances of events in varying situations and circumstances in order to determine the opinions, attitudes, preferences and perceptions of persons of interest to the researcher (Borg, 1981; Gay, 1992). In a similar vein, this approach enabled the researcher to investigate how interactions between sponsors and head teachers, teachers, BOG, PTA and education officials in religiously sponsored public secondary schools were leading to conflicts in schools' management. It also tried to link the sponsors' different areas of interaction with the mentioned groups and investigated the resultant effects of those interactions.

The saturated sampling technique was used. The researcher found this technique appropriate because it was in line with Orodho's (2004) observations that, small populations can form samples and be studied as distinct cases. This therefore meant that all the head teachers, teachers, Boards of Governors chairmen & Parents and Teachers' Association chairmen from the 38 religious sponsored public secondary schools formed the study sample. All the 6 education secretaries of the religious sponsors and all the assistant education officers manning the 5 educational divisions in the district were also part of the sample. Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) note that resource and time tend to be major constraints in deciding on the sample size to use. Therefore, in this study, a sample size of 467 respondents were sampled comprising of 38 BOG and 38 PTA chairmen, 38 head teachers, 6 education secretaries of the various religious denominations, 5 Assistant Education Offices and 342 teachers in the study area.

6.1 Data Analysis

Data were collected by use of questionnaires and in-depth interviews. The data collected through questionnaires and interviews were first subjected to pre-data analysis processes before appropriate statistics were applied to analyze the data and then the writing of the report.

6.2 Pre-Data Analysis Process

The gathered data from the questionnaires were validated, edited and then coded. The validation process enabled the researcher to determine the return rate of questionnaires which was over 90%, justifiable enough to allow analysis to go on. In editing, the instruments were scrutinized to determine the response rates. All the questionnaires were fully (100%) filled up, hence enough to provide the much needed data. Data from interviews and open-ended items in the questionnaires, constituting the qualitative data in form of words and phrases were transcribed and then arranged as per emerging themes. Some data were however quantified where possible along with quantitative data from structured questionnaire items. Finally, all quantitative data were coded, whereby categories of responses were identified, classified and then recorded or tabulated on a prepared sheet as per the research questions or objectives of the study. Percentages were used to show the proportion of respondents giving certain responses. The analyzed data were then presented using tables accompanied by appropriate descriptions or explanations.

6.3 Survey Returns

The study entailed the distribution of questionnaires to 456 respondents of which 365 (80.0%) were completed and returned as follows: 29 (76.3%) out of 38 were collected from head teachers, 285 (83.3%) out of 342 from teachers, 24 (63.2%) out of 27 from BOG Chairmen and 27 (71.1%) from PTA Chairmen. Table 2 summarizes the data from questionnaires' returns as per various categories of respondents.

Table 2: Questionnaire returns as per categories of respondents

Respondents	N	Returned questionnaire	Frequency
Head teachers	38	29	76.3%
Teachers	342	285	83.3%
BOG Chairmen	27	24	63.2%
PTA Chairmen	38	27	71.1%
Total	456	365	100%

Referring to Table 2, in overall, the questionnaire return rate of 80% was above the 70% Mugenda and Mugenda (1999) recommend for data analysis to go on in survey research design. Also the results in Table 2 imply that data were collected from various categories of respondents representing a variety of views from all stakeholders in education for valid conclusions.

7. Central Findings

7.1 Introduction

The purpose of the study was to examine the emergence of conflicts in the management of public secondary schools that were church sponsored. Results and discussion of the data collected during the study are presented in this section based on the objectives of the study or as guided by the research question.

The research question in this case was presented under the theme; “Specific conflicts from Sponsors in Public Secondary Schools’ Management”

7.2 Specific Conflicts from sponsors in Public Secondary Schools’ Management

The question sought to find out the specific issues of conflict in public religiously sponsored secondary schools’ management. The data for this theme were collected from BOG and PTA chairmen (using questionnaires) and Area Education Officers (AEOs) and sponsor’s Education Secretaries (Using Interviews).

7.3 Findings

According to the data obtained from open – ended questionnaire items in regard to specific conflicts from sponsors on public secondary schools’ management, all the BOG and PTA Chairmen concurred and pointed out the areas that fuelled the conflicts in schools as being:

- Management of finances;
- The elections of BOG Chairmen;
- New teachers’ recruitment;
- New students’ admissions;
- Materials assistance for sponsors from schools;
- Students’ freedom of worship.

Although most of the sponsors did not interfere with students’ admission to schools, one of the PTA chairmen said;

“After the general admission of students to join form one were done by the County Director of Education and Sub-County Education Officers, the schools then conducted their own admissions according to their church affiliations. In such schools, there were extra classrooms set aside to cater for that practice and most of them were over-enrolled with students... that such schools were performing well in academics hence students’ preference to join them.”

The above citation also confirms what the Assistant Education Officers indicated about the clandestine admissions of students in some schools being influenced by the religious sponsors. The Assistant Education Officers responded that areas of conflict in sponsored schools included:-

- Conflict on freedom of worship;
- Conflict on the appointments of Head teachers;
- Conflicts on mismanagement of finances;
- Conflicts regarding sponsor representation in the board;
- Conflicts on the admission of students to form one.

The AEOs indicated that the prevalence of these conflicts differed from one school to another. For example, the issue of freedom of worship mostly affected schools sponsored by the AIC, ACK and the SDA with minor incidents being reported in PAG sponsored schools, but did not affect the Orthodox sponsored schools at all. The appointment of head teachers was a major issue of conflict in Catholic, AIC and ACK sponsored schools. The AEO’s further responded that, the areas of conflict tended to become so because the sponsor sought to be more involved in matters that were better left to the schools’ management.

All the 5 (100%) AEOs concurred that, sponsors tended to be actively involved in some schools more than others or out-rightly were biased to some schools. When such schools were involved in anything they thought controversial, the sponsors responded to their situations faster than in other schools. That issue affected all sponsors across the board regardless of the church sponsor involved. On sponsor representation in the schools’ boards, the sponsor insisted on appointing their representatives to the BOG without the requisite academic qualifications. This is against the requirements of the Education Act that the sponsor to nominate four members with a form four level of education as the minimum academic qualification. The table below summarizes the findings of specific conflicts in schools’ management from Assistant Education Officer (AEOs).

Table 3: AEOs and Specific Conflicts in Public Secondary Schools' Management

Specific Conflicts	<i>f</i>	%
Conflicts on Head teachers' appointment	5	100%
Conflict on Form One admissions	5	100%
Conflict on staff Hiring	5	100%
Conflicts on management of finances	5	100%
Conflicts on Sponsors' BOG representation	5	100%

The findings from BOG chairmen pointed out specific issues of conflict as being;

- Disagreement over hiring of staff
- Issues of finance management
- Head teachers' appointments
- Students' freedom of ownership

The table below gives a summary of the findings from the BOGs;

Table 4: BOG Chairmen's Responses on Public Secondary Schools' Management Conflicts

	Sponsor				
	ACK	AIC	Roman Catholic	PAG	Others
Conflicts over staff hiring	11 (40.7%)	14 (58.3%)	12 (50%)	4 (16.6%)	5 (20.8%)
Conflicts over finances management	14 (51.8%)	15 (62.5%)	21 (87.5%)	4 (16.6%)	5 (20.8%)
Conflicts over student's worship	17 (70.8%)	22 (87.5%)	12 (44.4%)	2 (8.3%)	1 (4.5%)
Conflicts over Head teachers' appointments	16 (59.2%)	21 (91.6%)	16 (66.6%)	9 (37.5%)	3 (12.5%)
Conflicts over Teacher's recruitment	12 (44.4%)	18 (75%)	14 (58.3%)	6 (25%)	4 (16.6%)

The table shows that conflicts over issues of management of finances mostly came up in catholic sponsored schools at 87.5%, then AIC at 62.5% and ACK at 51.8%. The conflicts associated with recruitment of new teachers mostly came up in AIC sponsored schools at 75% when catholic at 58.3% and ACK at 44.4%. Appointments of head teachers were mostly a conflict in AIC sponsored schools at 87.5%, then Catholic at 66.6% and ACK at 59.2%. The issue of freedom of worship for students was another conflict that mostly manifested itself in AIC Sponsored schools at 91.6% followed by ACK at 70.8% and Catholic at 44.4%.

Findings from Education Secretaries' responses indicated that management conflicts that arose in their schools included those associated with misappropriation of school funds by head teachers, BOGs and Educational Officers' incompetence in

schools' management and head teachers' appointments. The table below summarizes the responses.

Table 5: Education Secretaries' responses on specific conflicts in schools' Management

Conflict	<i>f</i>	%
Conflicts over interpretation of Education Act	3	50%
Conflict over head teachers' appointment	6	100%
Conflicts over misappropriation of school funds	6	100%
Conflicts over BOGs' laxity in schools management	6	100%
Conflict over Education Officers incompetence in schools' management	5	83.3%

According to 3 (50%) educational secretaries, at other times problems arose because there was poor interpretation of the Education Act from both the Head teachers and the sponsors. All the educational secretaries interviewed, 6 (100%) indicated that appointments of head teachers without them being consulted was another conflict that affected the management of the schools they sponsored. Misappropriation of school funds and lack of sound management skills by Boards of Governors was indicated by all 6 (100%) education secretaries as being among the conflicts that affected schools' management. Another group of 5 (83.3%) said that education officers were incompetent in handling matters pertaining to management of secondary schools, therefore fuelling school management conflicts.

8. Discussion

The preceding findings indicate that there were varied conflicts depending on the type of sponsor involved. Responses from Boards of Governors' chairmen revealed that policies of the various sponsors were the ones that led to most conflicts. The policy of the African Inland Church (AIC) concerning freedom of worship was not acceptable to parents and students therefore becoming a conflict.

This concurred with the findings of Thornton and Ryan (2006) whose study of conflict of religion in America's Public schools had revealed that parents usually sued schools where religious rights of their children were not respected. The end result most of the time was occurrence of conflicts.

According to the Parents and Teachers' Association (PTA) Chairmen, the sponsors' involvement in the management of finances became a conflict when they got involved by always monitoring any projects that were being undertaken in schools. In other schools, the sponsors demanded to check schools' books of accounts, a practice which both the BOG and PTA thought was beyond the mandate of the sponsor since it

was not provided for in the Education Act. They did that by instructing head teachers to effect the same yet it was against the Education Act.

The PTA chairmen also felt that religious sponsors interfered with their work when they tried to supervise physical developments in schools. These findings concurred with those of Sakaja's (1986) study which had studied the role of the PTA in the promotion of education in Aldai Division of Nandi District. The study had revealed that there were conflicts between BOGs and PTAs, which mainly centered on the management of Development Funds.

The issue of religious freedom being denied students was serious especially since it is clearly spelt out in the Education Act how issues of worship should be conducted in schools. If therefore students were being denied chance to worship, it was an indication that the head teachers and sponsors involved did not understand the Education Act.

The findings from the Assistant Education Officers indicated that head teachers were also to blame for the conflicts being custodians of the Education Act. They were supposed to be in a better position to interpret how such issues were supposed to be resolved. By allowing situations to deteriorate to the extent of confrontation, means that they were not conversant with the guidelines given hence could not give good guidance over the same. This is in line with Kiniale's (2000) study which indicated that the head teacher is charged with the broad role of transforming the culture of the school, changing the attitudes of the collaborative group, planning strategies, creating awareness and making adjustments in the general organization of the school. The head teacher should therefore be a person who is conversant with all current issues in education and generally be an informed person.

The study also revealed that BOGs' contributed to the emergence of conflicts in their schools by not following the Education Act when executing their duties as schools' managers. By not doing that, they had created loopholes in schools' management which were being exploited by head teachers and religious sponsors to result into conflicts. This is in line with Chege's (2004) study which had sought to find out the effects of teacher' recruitment on the teaching profession in Koibatek Sub-County. The study had revealed that most of the people appointed to be members of BOG were not committed, competent or experienced enough to handle the management and development of education institutions. That was because they were most of the time appointed without those issues being taken into consideration. Their incompetence therefore was exploited by other interested groups like PTAs, Head teachers and Sponsors.

The findings indicated that the conflicts found in religiously sponsored public secondary schools included those that came about because of misunderstandings in recruitment of new teachers, management of finances, hiring of staff, appointment of

head teachers, students' freedom of worship and sponsors' demand for materials assistance from the schools.

It was also revealed that, although the magnitude of the occurrences of conflicts involving the mentioned areas was not uniform across all the sponsors, it however emerged that they were all affected. While one aspect of the issue for the conflicts affected one sponsor greatly, another was just slightly affected but they were however common to all.

9. Summary, Conclusions And Recommendations

Presented here are a summary of the study findings, conclusions and recommendations.

9.1 Summary of findings on specific conflicts in Church Sponsored public secondary schools

- BOG and PTA chairmen and AEOs concurred that the specific areas where conflicts were evident in schools' management included management of finances, the election of BOG Chairmen, recruitment of staff, appointments of head teachers, admission of students, assistance to sponsors and students' freedom of worship. Furthermore, the AEOs said conflicts were evident in the area of sponsors' representation in the boards whereby sponsors wanted to have a strong say on who were to be members in the board.
- Education secretaries said that specific conflicts pitting the sponsor against head teachers, BOGs and other stakeholders included financial management, tendering procedures, lack of physical development in schools and questionable behaviors of teachers.

9.2 Conclusions of the Study

Based on the study findings, this study concluded that specific conflicts touched on;

- Appointment of head teachers
- Financial management and misappropriation of funds
- Admission of new students
- Recruitment of staff
- Utilization of schools' resources.

9.3 Way Forward / Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Head teachers to undergo in-service training on financial management so that they deal with conflicts arising from religious sponsors on mismanagement of funds.
- The Ministry of Education should make religious sponsors aware of their role in admission of students as defined in the Education Act to avoid conflicts that arise in the same from sponsors
- On the appointment of head teachers in religious sponsored public secondary schools, the regulations should be adhered to as defined in the Education Act to avoid the sponsors' domination of the appointments, which causes conflicts. The same should be applied in the appointments of BOG chairmen and even members to the board.

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